

THE USE OF PERSONAL DEIXIS IN THE STORY "THE NOSE" BY NIKOLAI VASILIEVICH GOGOL

Alikulova Shaxnoza Abdimuminovna

1st Year master student of UESS

Abstract. This study explored the application of deixis in Nikolai Vasilievich Gogol's novel *The Nose*. Deixis is a part of pragmatics that discusses the context in an utterance. The purpose of this study was to find out the types of deixis used in the story and to analyze the function of the deixis found in the story *The Nose*. In analyzing deixis, this study used Yule's theory (1996) which divides deixis into three categories: person deixis, spatial deixis, and temporal deixis. Person deixis is used to show people, spatial deixis is used to show location, and temporal deixis is used to show time. This study belongs to qualitative research with descriptive qualitative because the data was obtained in the form of words or utterances. In collecting the data, this study used the documentation method which was carried out through note-taking and reading strategies. The results showed that there were three types of deixis found in the story *The Nose*. They were person deixis, spatial deixis, and temporal deixis. There were a total of 608 deixis data found. Among them were 502 person deixis, including 151 first person deixis, 92 second person deixis, and 259 third person deixis. Meanwhile, there were 75 spatial deixis data and 32 temporal deixis data.

Keywords: pragmatics, deixis, function, story.

INTRODUCTION

Pragmatics is the study of how things are communicated and interpreted. Yule (1996) explains that the study of pragmatics examines how a speaker or writer conveys meaning and how a listener or reader understands it. To put it another way, the focus of pragmatic analysis is on the speaker's meaning rather than the meaning of individual words or sentence. According to Leech (1983), the study of how words are understood in relation to the internal context of the words themselves is known as pragmatics. Thus, pragmatics provides an understanding of what the individual is saying, by focusing on the implicit meaning. Moreover, Levinson (1983) states that the study of pragmatics focuses on the facets of the interaction between language and situation that are important to the creation of grammars. That is, in pragmatics studies, the relation of language and situation affects how grammar is used. One of the branches in pragmatics that deals with the expression or context of a sentence is called deixis. Deixis is a term to describe people, places, and time. It has a reference that changes depending on the context of the situation. Levinson (1983) explains that the phenomena of deixis serves as the best example of how language structures convey the connection between language and context. Thus, deixis, as a part of pragmatics studies, aims to clarify how language and context relate to one another in terms of linguistic structure. As part of pragmatics, the study of deixis plays a

crucial role in communication. It can help people in interpreting the meaning of a particular sentence based on the context. However, when using deixis, we must also know who is speaking and who is listening. In that way, we can identify the meaning of deixis in the utterance. Anggara (2017) states that deixis contributes to the comprehension of how language is used in conversation.

Therefore, we need to understand deixis as part of pragmatics study because when we can understand language in conversation, it can make it easier for us to know the meaning contained in an utterance. Deixis can be discovered in a variety of sources such as in song lyrics and in a classroom setting. Deixis, however, can also be found in other literary works, including articles and speeches as well as movies, books, short stories, and poems. In addition, we can also find deixis in our everyday life where we interact with other people. For example, in a classroom where teachers and students interact with each other. In the communication process, it is very possible for us to find the use of deixis from both sides. The researchers choose deixis as the research subject because by understanding deixis, we can find out the intent of the speaker's utterances. To know the reference of a word or phrase, we must first know the context of the utterance. Without the context of speech, we do not know who the person is referring to, where the intended place is, and when the intended time is. For example, when someone says, "He is very kind", as a listener, we do not know who the "he" is meant by the speaker. Without the context of speech, we do not know who the speaker is referring to. Well, this is where deixis plays a role in showing who the person is referring to in that utterance. The researchers in this study examined deixis in one of the literary works in the form of story with the title "The Nose" by Gogol. It is a satirical work that was written between 1835-1836 by Gogol and consists of 34 pages. , "The Nose" tells the story of a St. Petersburg official whose nose leaves his face and develops a life of its own. The story was originally published in *The Contemporary*, a literary journal owned by Alexander Pushkin. The use of a nose as the main source of conflict could have been due to Gogol's own experience with an oddly shaped nose, which was often the subject of self-deprecating jokes in letters. The use of iconic landmarks in the story, as well as its sheer absurdity, has made "The Nose" an important part of St. Petersburg's literary tradition. The researchers choose the novel "The Nose" as the object of the study because there has never been any research related to deixis on this novel. In addition, there are many deictic expressions that can be found in this novel. It is widely illustrated in the utterances or dialogue between characters in the novel.

Types of deixis Deixis has several types which also indicate different things. Yule (1996) claims that deixis can be grouped into three categories, as shown below: Person deixis Person deixis is also known as personal deixis. It is used to indicate a person that the speaker or writer is referring to. In communication, person deixis is the most significant aspect. It is because the roles of participants in speech events, such as speakers, recipients, and other

entities, are encoded in person deixis. Yule (1996, p.10) defines that “person deixis clearly operates on a basic three-part division, exemplified by pronouns for first person (I), second person (you), and third person (she, he, it).” Spatial deixis Spatial deixis indicates the relative placement of individuals and objects. According to Cruse (2000), there are only two terms of spatial deictic system in English which are known as proximal and distal. They have different functions. Proximal indicates a location which is close to the speaker (for example: this and here). Distal, on the other hand, indicates a location which is distant from the speaker (for example: that and there). Temporal deixis Temporal deixis is used to identify a time. It is a word that denotes the precise moment at which the speaker's utterances were made.

Data Analysis

The data analysis method used in conducting this research was suggested by Miles and Huberman (1994) who state that qualitative analysis consists of three main stages which are known as follows:

Data reduction Data reduction is the first stage of analysis. It is a method that involves retrieval, centralization, simplification, abstraction, and writing down of the information that has been collected. As part of the analysis, data reduction has an important role because it can be used to eliminate irrelevant parts and organize the data so that the final findings can be reached and validated by the researchers. A literary work in the form of a novel served as the study's source of data. Thus, at this stage, the researchers first analyzed the data by choosing the utterances of the characters that contain deixis. The researchers then concentrated on determining the kind of deixis that was present in the utterances. The varieties of deixis were then divided into groups based on Yule's theory by the researchers. The researchers then examined the deixis function that was present in the utterances. **Data display** The second phase in qualitative data analysis is data display. A display is a collection of information that has been carefully arranged so that it allows drawing conclusions and actions to be taken. The data display can facilitate the process of understanding and analyzing the data that has been obtained for further evaluation of the data one by one.

Conclusion drawing conclusions is the last stage of data analysis. It requires a step back to understand what is implied from the analyzed data and its implications for the research problems. The researchers conclude the meaning of the data displayed during this stage. The final conclusion must then be verified in order for it to be completely accounted for. In this stage, the researchers drew conclusions about the results of the research that has been done based on research problems regarding the use of deixis.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION Findings Types of deixis in the story “The Nose” Person deixis Person deixis is a type of deixis that is used to show people or things.

This type of deixis is further divided into three parts, namely first person, second person, and third person. 1) First person deixis First person refers to the

speakers themselves or, to put it another way, the person who makes the statement. The two forms of the first person are singular and plural first person. The words such as I, my, me, mine, myself are indicated as first person singular. Meanwhile, the words such as we, us, our, ours, ourselves are indicated as first-person plural. Based on the research results, all the pronouns mentioned are found in this type of deixis, as shown in the table below.

Table 1

First Person Dexis	Amount
I	103
ME	17
My	20
Mine	1
Myself	9
WE	1
Us	
Our	
Ours	
Ourselves	
Total	151

Function of deixis in the novel “The Nose”

Extract 1 “I don’t want any coffee today, Praskovya Osipovna’, said Ivan Yakovlevich, ‘I’ll make do with some hot rolls and onion instead.’ (Here I must explain that Ivan Yakovlevich would really have liked to have had some coffee as well, but knew it was quite out of the question to expect both coffee and rolls since.” (p.1) In the extract above, first person deixis was found. The word “I” is a singular pronoun that refers to the speaker of the utterance. Depending on the context of the situation, the statement above was said by Ivan Yakovlivich..

Extract 2 “And the missing person was a household serf of yours?” ” (p 29)

In the extract above, the first second person singular was found. Based on the context of the utterance.

Extract 3 “I beg your pardon ,sir,he said,”but have you lost your nose?.” (p.36) In the extract above, second person deixis was found. It was an utterance that was uttered by Ivan. Based on the context of the utterance, Ivan spoke to police- officer. Here, the word “your” refers to police-officer as the addressee. The word itself indicates a singular pronoun and it functions as a possessive adjective as it indicates Ivan's possession which is police -offecer.

CONCLUSION The study's findings indicate personal deixis, according to Yule’s theory, are found in the story “The Nose” by Nikolai Vasilievich Gogol. There are a total of 888 deixis data found. Person deixis is the most frequently found data with a total of 800 data, consisting of 368 first person deixis data, 305 second person deixis data, and 127 third person deixis dataThe person deixis found includes first person singular such as “I”, “me”, “my”, “mine”, “myself”,

first person plural such as “we”, “us”, “our”, “ours”, “ourselves”, second person singular such as “you”, “your”, “yours”, “yourself”, second person plural “you”, third person singular such as “he”, “she”, “it”, “him”, “her” “his”, “himself”, “herself”, and third person plural such as “they”, “them”. The deixis found has a different function because the reference always changes according to the context of the utterance. It depends on who, where, and when the utterance was said. The function of person deixis found is as a subject, object, possessive adjective, possessive pronoun, and reflexive pronoun.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullah, M. (2015). Deixis: A Pragmatics Analysis. *Language in India*, 15(12), 3-9.
2. Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
3. Cruse, A. (2000). *Meaning in Language: An Introduction to Semantics and Pragmatics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Crystal, D. (1997). *English as a global language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
4. Erdanova, Z. A., & Kulmuhamedova, L. (2024, October). The Depiction of Women in Uzbek and English Literature: A Comparative Analysis. In *Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit* (pp. 55-57).
5. Dylgjeri, A., & Kazazi, L. (2013). Deixis in modern linguistics and outside. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies* 2(4), 87-87.
6. Fasold, R. W., & Connor-Linton, J. (2006). *An introduction to language and linguistics*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
7. Erdanova, Z. A. (2024). STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC CONCEPT OF “TERMIOSYSTEM”. *Western European Journal of Medicine and Medical Science*, 2(11), 150-154.
8. Gogol N.V “The nose and a May Nght” Dorlion Yayinlari Ocak 2021
9. Hidayah, A. (2019). A Deixis Analysis of Song Lyrics in Back To You by Selena Gomes. *Surakarta English and Literature Journal*, 2(2), 47-55.
10. Huang, Y. (2007). *Pragmatics*. Oxford TextBooks In Linguistics. By Oxford University Press Inc, New York. The United States, Published.
11. Leech, G. (1983). *Principle of Pragmatic*. London: Longman.